

Table 3. Secondary data information, 2020 and 2021. Species refers the dominant species, as inferred from morphological characteristics of captured and released insects²⁹. ST refers to sunset times at collection site. Temperatures were measured at collection sites (typical accuracy $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) but may vary over the course of the recording.

ID	Species	ST	T (°F)	T (°C)	Camera	Notes
s0521uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:21			Fusion	Used for technical validation
s0522uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:22			Fusion	ibid.
s0523uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:23			Fusion	ibid.
s0524uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:23	72	22	Fusion	ibid.
s0525uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:24	72	22	Fusion	ibid.
s0526uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:25	70	21	Fusion	ibid.
s0527uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:25			Fusion	ibid.
s0528uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:26			Fusion	ibid.
s0601ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>	20:45			Fusion	ibid.
s0603ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>	20:46			Fusion	ibid.
s0606ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>				Fusion	ibid.
s0608ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>				Fusion	ibid.
s0609ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>	20:49	68	20	Fusion	ibid.
s0610ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>	20:49	66	19	Fusion	ibid.
s0611ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>	20:50			Fusion	ibid.
s0612ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>	20:50			Fusion	ibid.
s0613ic	<i>Photinus carolinus</i>	20:51			Fusion	ibid.
s1601io	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i>	20:15			Fusion	
s1602io	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i>	20:16			Fusion	
s1604io	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i>	20:18			Fusion	
s1605mx	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i> (mixed, see notes)	20:18			Fusion	also <i>Pyractomena angulata</i> , <i>dispersa</i> , <i>sinuata</i> , <i>marginalis</i>
s1606mx	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i> (mixed, see notes)	20:19			Fusion	ibid. and <i>Photuris</i> sp.
s1607mx	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i> (mixed, see notes)	20:20			Fusion	ibid.
s1609mx	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i> (mixed, see notes)	20:21			Fusion	ibid. and <i>Photinus consimilis</i>
s1610mx	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i> (mixed, see notes)	20:21			Fusion	ibid.
s1612mx	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i> (mixed, see notes)	20:22			Fusion	ibid.
s1613uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:55	78 - 74	26 - 23	Fusion	Crescent moon overhead but dense canopy
s1613io	<i>Photinus obscurellus</i>	20:23			Fusion	possible <i>Pyractomena marginalis</i> and <i>Photuris</i>
s1614ig	<i>Photinus greeni</i>	20:23			Fusion	
s1615ux	<i>Photuris</i> sp.	20:24			Fusion	
s1615uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:56	68 - 60	20 - 16	Fusion	Crescent moon overhead but dense canopy
s1617uf	<i>Photuris frontalis</i>	20:56	68 - 61	20 - 16	Fusion	Moon first quarter, low in sky
s1617ux	<i>Photuris</i> sp.	20:25			Fusion	
s1618ux	<i>Photuris</i> sp.	20:25			Fusion	
s1619ux	<i>Photuris</i> sp.	20:25			Fusion	
s1706ig	<i>Photinus greeni</i>	20:25			Fusion	
s1710im	<i>Photinus marginellus</i>	20:23			Fusion	
s1711im	<i>Photinus marginellus</i>	20:22			Fusion	
s1723im	<i>Photinus marginellus</i>	20:13			Fusion	
s1806ik	<i>Photinus knulli</i>	19:15	82	28	Max	Relative humidity (RH):80-65%
s1809ik	<i>Photinus knulli</i>	19:12	77	25	Max	RH: 65%
s1810ik	<i>Photinus knulli</i>	19:11	86	30	Max	RH: 75%, frequent lightning (no rain)
s1813ik	<i>Photinus knulli</i>	19:08	77	25	Max	Site flooded two days prior; RH: 70%